

ASSESSMENT OF MYCOLOGICAL SAFETY OF FODDER PLANTS IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

Flora and fauna of Azerbaijan, as well as climate types, are different in the researched areas. For example, a total of 22% of the mycobiota typical of Azerbaijan can be found in the Absheron plain located in the Greater Caucasus. Although 8 of the 11 climate types on Earth are found in Azerbaijan, the dry subtropical climate is typical for Kura-Araz and the Absheron part of the Greater Caucasus, and the humid climate type is characteristic for the southern region. A mild climate is observed on the slopes of the Greater and Lesser Caucasus, which are mostly covered with forests, and on the high mountain tops, a cold climate is observed. In all of these, the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan, which is not so large, determines the formation of ecologically different senoses and biotopes. This, in turn, determines the characteristics of planting and spreading of both cultivated and wild plants in different areas with different quantitative indicators.

Keywords: mycobiota, ecology, biotope, fodder plant

Fungi involved in the causation of diseases observed in this or that plant differ not only in terms of species composition and participation combination, but also in the ecotrophic relations of the causative agent, the symptoms of the diseases it causes, as well as the impact of the diseases they cause on the environment [1]. In general, it should be noted that although fungi are simple and undifferentiated as the oldest organisms among eukaryotes, they differ not only from eukaryotes but also from prokaryotes due to the complexity of the functions they perform [2], the effect of the diseases they cause, and in all cases, the diseases caused by fungi are similar to other diseases. Compared to organisms, they are characterized as being evaluated in a negative direction. This feature is the first reason why it is necessary to ensure the mycological safety of products with different purposes, including feed.

The second reason for ensuring the mycological safety of fodder plants, as well as fodder produced for this purpose, is related to the deterioration of fodder plants and the quality indicators of products obtained from them with the metabolites formed by fungi as a result of their life activity. Thus, as a result of their life activities, fungi synthesize exogenous metabolites with different effects, which stay on or enter the plants where the fungus lives and feeds [6,7]. The introduced metabolites are mainly caused by endophytic fungi, many of which do not cause serious damage to the host plant, and sometimes the metabolites produced by them have beneficial effects on other plants as well as in various fields [2,8]. Among the metabolites that either remain on the plant cells or enter them, those that have a toxic effect are commonly called mycotoxins. Mycotoxins are compounds that are not so large molecular, but have a stable and stable composition, synthesized by fungi as secondary metabolites [2,5] and mainly have a positive effect on the advantage of the fungus that synthesizes it in the struggle for survival and adaptation to the environment. Based on the analysis of literature data, it is now known that there are 500 names of mycotoxins synthesized by fungi [3], and most of these mycotoxins (for example, Aflatoxin, ochratoxin, zeralonone, deoxydinivanelone, fumonisin,

citricin, etc.) lead to negative consequences for living things, including humans. They can open. So, they are carcinogenic, mutagenic, teratogenic, allergenic, etc. have characteristics. In addition, the temperature factor plays an important role in the degree of mycotoxin contamination of plants, including those of feed importance, and this issue is of particular importance in the conditions of global climate change, which humanity has already begun to feel.

One of the reasons for ensuring mycological safety is related to the control of factors that positively affect the development of fungi during the storage of dried fodder plants. Thus, the main indicators for the development of fungi, especially mold fungi, are humidity and suitable temperature in the environment. In such conditions, fungi multiply rapidly and cause moldiness of food crops, reduction of nutrients and enrichment with mycotoxins.

Thus, it is clear from the above that there are at least 3 reasons that require ensuring the mycological safety of the use of plants, including forage, and the presence of each of them leads to negative consequences that limit the effectiveness of their use. It is not a coincidence that today, all over the world, the points of attention regarding ensuring the safety of the use of plants in mycological aspects mainly consist of these.

According to what has been said, if we touch on the research conducted in this direction in Azerbaijan, it can be noted first that until our research, fodder plants have not been scientifically comprehensively studied from the point of view of these reasons, although the mycobiota of plants, the toxic activity of toxigenic fungi involved in its formation, etc. numerous research materials [9,10,11] are found in Azerbaijan regarding its characteristics. As mentioned above, the results of these studies are not sufficient in terms of ensuring the mycological safety of the use of fodder plants in Azerbaijan today, so the studies conducted on the reasons for the need to ensure mycological safety, especially those related to the 1st and 3rd reasons, are mostly episodic in nature. Although the studies on cause 2 are somewhat extensive, they are also

insufficient to make full generalizations on this aspect, not least because of the small number of forage plants in that study. The work carried out in this aspect has been touched upon in the previous part of the work, but it would be appropriate to clarify the issues related to the extent to which they are useful in ensuring mycological safety. First of all, if we consider the research conducted on the first reason, i.e. the fungi causing disease in fodder plants and limiting their activities, it is clear that no systematic studies have been conducted in this regard, and in a number of literatures, information has been taken from other sources and applied to the fodder plants of Azerbaijan. For example, fusarium wilt, spotting, rust, wilting, etc. found in fodder plants distributed in Azerbaijan in a number of sources. such diseases are mentioned [12,13, 15], but the degree of spread of the causative agents of those diseases on a specific fodder plant, its phytopathological activity, etc. There are no research materials about its characteristics. A similar opinion can be said about the publication of the danger of this or that disease in the results obtained in those studies. All these are almost completely insufficient in terms of providing the first criterion of the conducted researches.

It can be noted that the second criterion, i.e., the data obtained regarding the study of toxic metabolites produced by fungi as a result of life activity, is insufficient in terms of ensuring the mycological safety of fodder plants. The reason for this is that in the researches conducted in Azerbaijan in this direction, toxicogenicity (both phyto- and zoo-toxic) activity was studied not according to a specific mycotoxin, but according to the effect of the sum of exogenous metabolites obtained from fungi on the germination ability of plant seeds or the viability of seedlings [14,16 ,5,9,10]. This does not allow us to determine which specific toxin of the fungus causes negative consequences. True, these data create a certain impression about the fungi that can cause toxicosis, but it is not enough for a complete solution of the issue today.

As for the third criterion, the situation related to it is at a lower level compared to the others. Thus, the analysis of the literature data showed that there was no information on the effect of the moisture content of fodder plants during storage, the quantity of mycobiota at the time of storage, and the effect of the symptoms of the disease on the storage process. All this allows us to note that ensuring the mycological safety of fodder plants is an important issue, but the results obtained up to our research do not allow us to generalize these issues.

Thus, the number and species composition of the mycobiota of cultivated and wild fodder plants in the world, including in Azerbaijan, the diseases caused by pathogenic species involved in the formation of mycobiota, as well as certain studies related to the study of indicators important for ensuring the mycological safety of fodder plants when using them although it was carried out, today there are enough unclarified aspects of the problem, and their study is of great importance both in terms of the existence of global problems felt

by everyone in the modern era, and in terms of the increase in demand for products of various purposes corresponding to the increase in the number of the world population, so that the work presented is directed to the solution of existing problems in this direction.

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